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IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PILGRIMAGE TOURISM IN OUR COUNTRY, IMAM AL-BUKHARI SHRINE OF THE COMPLEX PLACE

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Abstract: *This article explores ways to shape and develop tourism infrastructure for pilgrims at Imam Al-Bukhari Complex.*

Keywords: *Tourism, Pilgrimage Tourism, Infrastructure, Pilgrimage.*

The world in the economy tourism fast developing and income according to leader from fields one is considered Last in years tourism the world in export his own huge contribution have it has been and the whole world gross internal of the product is 11%. In particular, the successes achieved in Uzbekistan on the ground the economy liberalization deepening, the country modernization, all fields, in particular service to show of the field sustainable development of tourism, one of the leading industries. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev noted: "Uzbekistana convenient country for both travel and pilgrimage. Because mother is whole in our land our ancestors, who are known and famous in the world, have settled down forever. They are There is great interest in the rich spiritual and cultural heritage left by the international community. For the further development of the industry, first of all, the improvement of the necessary infrastructure condition"

Ancient of Samarkand architecture monuments with met Muslim tourists often another sacred wanting to go to the shrine they stay. This shrine, especially Muslim from countries visit orderedIt is very valuable for tourists. Because, here, Islam with its merits the world famous scholar Abu Abdullah Muhammad ibn Ismail ibn Ibrahim al Bukhari your majesty mausoleum is located. Burial of Imam al-Bukhari the place where it happened is the village of Khartang in the Payariq district, where the Khan of Bukhara is located Abdullah Khan mosque built by too saved.

Initiatives of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev with this complex big landscaping works in progress. In particular,

President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, April 14-15, 2017 during his visit to Samarkand region in the territory of the Imam Bukhari complex assignment on the construction of an international scientific center based on

international experience given was That's it relationship with to the complex connection from the area 5,8 hectares land square, a scientific center and 3 three-story residential buildings in front of the center construction for separate given of our President current year 17-18 March days Imam Bukhari with the task he gave during his visit to Samarkand region project-proposal for the reconstruction of the complex and the master plan-project of the village of Khartang approved .

now Imam Bukhari's grave to Uzbekistan visit commanding it has become a blessed shrine for guests. Today, Samarkand Imam Al-Bukhari complex is located in Payariq district of the region It is becoming a "city of pilgrimage". The personality of Imam Bukhari in the Islamic world incomparable Name didn't know Muslim almost no. His service all A Muslim confesses and visits the shrine of Hazrat at least once in his life wants to do.

Pilgrimage of tourism increase of our country material potential more increases. Specialists according to if only one Imam Bukhari complex town per year 100 — 150 a thousand foreign tourists acceptance if he does of them the amount will be approximately 300-400 million dollars. The complex, which is being renovated, is already from the countries neighboring our country except Saudi Arabia, Turkey, Indonesia, Malaysia, Pakistan It is in this regard that tourism companies of the countries show great interest numbers just not assumptions clarifies.

Imam Bukhari complex is a place of pilgrimage for tourists in our country it will be the first pilgrimage town with all infrastructure created. This After the complex and its surroundings are completely rebuilt and renovated, the complex internal and begins to receive a large flow of foreign tourism. In particular, Malaysia 100,000 tourists are expected to come from it. of Malaysian pilgrims Most of them want to visit the mausoleum of Imam Bukhari before Hajj. This shows that two and a half million Muslims go to Hajj from Malaysia in one year goes If we reach the level where we can receive so many pilgrims, our President initiative of pilgrimage tourism that started with development take will come.

Pilgrimage tourism is a modern tourism industry indispensable part is considered In the world one half billion more Muslim there is If mother that's it Half of the Muslims collected authentic hadiths, the second most reliable of Islam to visit the shrines of His Holiness Imam Bukhari, who created the source it comes, it will have a positive effect on our economy. In our country the infrastructure for receiving so many pilgrims has not yet been formed. Religious, historical and cultural monuments visit a certain region or city important for ordering. He was under state protection in France of monuments about 60 percent too religious tourism objects is considered

Religious to tourism has been common of interest development in Uzbekistan ancient to history go tight That's it pride with to emphasize must the world civilization

to science in general of mankind too spiritual, too to material advancement incomparable share added ancestors about history us generously respected by: each old our land sacred each old our land shrine Greatour ancestors, the dreams and goals of our people, the power, the scope of thinking , spiritual the world taste level, capacity and culture manifestation makes depending on their intelligence and intelligence, the world will count on us, we will be judged will give. We religion today in the mask to error to the satisfaction exactly mother that's it ancestors the way and capacity, wisdom with fed against we fight This in the struggle they are it will be our weapon, evidence, flag . Our president is in our country pilgrimage tourism more separate to development attention looking at at the core too mother that's it good goals incarnate. Last 2 year inside in Uzbekistan holy shrines pilgrimage did tourists, also foreign from hand religious and the number of people traveling for the purpose of pilgrimage has increased significantly. in 2018 Compared to 2017, the number of foreign citizens who came to the Republic of Uzbekistan is 2.3 times increased.

The main part of these travelers is accounted for by the CIS countries will come. Foreign citizens who came to the Republic of Uzbekistan from the CIS countries 6015.9 thousand people, which is 93.5% of the total number of visitors 417.1 thousand people (or 6.5%) visited from distant foreign countries ordered. The main part of foreign citizens who came to the Republic of Uzbekistan 2456.9 thousand people from the Republic of Kazakhstan (38.2%), 1700.7 from Tajikistan a thousand people (26.4%), 1101.5 from Kyrgyzstan thousand people (17.1%), from Russia 460.2 a thousand person (7.2 %). Long foreign from the states while From Turkey 74,8 a thousand person (1.2 %), From China 37.1 a thousand person (0.6 %), South From Korea 32.7 a thousand

people (0.5%), 22.2 thousand people from India (0.3%), 19.1 thousand people from Germany person (0.3 %), From Japan 17.2 thousand people (0.3 %) visit ordered.

The main pilgrimage tourism has three forms: pilgrimage, on religious themes excursions, pilgrims and tourists which merge specialized excursions. Muslims for to visit to go – Islamic monuments to visit, to visit holy places and to develop donation to do in order to religious areas pilgrimage they do. In our country this pilgrimage that was named and these are the world of Muslims to our country aspiration strengthen no doubt. already pilgrimage only watch it's not: she is, the most first of all feeling the spirit of the great, receiving strength from the spiritual environment, the status of the great and attitude, aliveness and life about the most eternal truth understanding the heart that's it with truth is enrichment.

From visiting holy places and monuments in Uzbekistan consists of has been "small Hajj program formation and regions 2019-2029 of socio-economic

development in the years development of tourism on the way out the following issues account get must we think:

- in the regions cultural heritage of objects local lists formation and constantly updated provide;
- local power and belongs to field employees with in collaboration in the regions is located historical in the garden and to monuments take going infrastructure formation in order to their electron maps, passport and cadastre documents preparation;
- in the regions is located holy steps and monuments touristicto programs input take action this ancient memorials history and he on the ground preserved traditional culture widely promoted reach;
- tour operator and unexplored historical sites and monuments in the regions another belongs to specialists with together research reach and datacreate a database;
- higher education in the field of tourism teaching specialized subjects in their countries historical monuments and monuments located in the territory during the process closely with introduction according to practical lessons organize to do;
- tourism of the field essence, his importance, development organized various seminars and trainings on the results, economic and social functionsto do and others.

Assessing the current state of tourism, it is important to note that in Uzbekistan of infrastructure development level foreign fifty of tourists needs full satisfy can't. Infrastructure that it is not developed the previous administration did not allow to encourage competition and improvement command system is the cause. The infrastructure is not developed enough increase the flow of tourists and, accordingly, foreign currency income cannot be multiplied. Based on this, the state of the infrastructure of tourism development and country image to form directly effect shows. First of all, it should be noted that the Republic of Uzbekistan to independence until achieved to tourism enough attention not directed.

of the Republic touristic potential right objective data and advertising it didn't happen at all. Tourism, service and entertainment infrastructure underdeveloped to tourists service show level low being of the world it can be said that there were no contacts with leading tourist enterprises. Summary in place that's it to say maybe tourism today's in the day the most profitable from fieldsis recognized as one. In this respect, tourism by most countries development about one how much programs work coming out. Our country economic potential in raising tourism field too big to opportunities have Basically international tourism development about done being increased affairs as a result pilgrimage tourism in our country leader from fields to one becomes.

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